

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Transparency and Global Initiatives in the Face of Natural Resource Depletion in Sub-Saharan Africa**Seun Adebawale Adebajo^{1*}, Olugbode²

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Abstract

This research focuses on Natural Resource Depletion in Sub-Saharan Africa, as well as ways to overcome it, with a particular focus on the role of transparency in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The transparency initiative is a global initiative aimed at eradicating corruption, ensuring accountability, and assisting participating countries in developing quality budgets that will ensure a good standard of living for their citizens now and in the future. Hausman test was applied and a fixed panel regression model was specified which reveal that there is a significant relationship between GDP per capita, inflation, the EITI dummy, and the transparency indicator is established using a panel regression model. The results show that the model fits the data well and can be used to forecast future economic growth in SSA countries that participate in the EITI scheme. The fixed effect model also shows that the Transparency indicators such as voice and accountability, and corruption have a positive significant impact on the economic growth of the 10 SSA countries under consideration, indicating that transparency is a critical factor in determining good economic performance. Meanwhile, diagnostic tests such as normality test was performed, with satisfactory results, indicating that the model is very robust and reliable. Meanwhile, inflation have positive significant impact while natural resources show a negative significant influence on the economic growth of all the 10 Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) in the EITI scheme which can be attributed to the natural economic depletion. Then, using correlation analysis, it was discovered that there is a strong link between transparency indicators (voice and accountability, corruption as well as quality of budget, and fiscal management) and economic growth. This suggests that the greater the transparency, the more natural resource constraints will be overcome, and SSA countries participating in the EITI scheme will achieve greater economic performance.

Keywords: Hausman test, Fixed effect Panel regression model, EITI, GDP Per Capita, Transparency, Correlation analysis, SSA.

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1.0 Background of the study

As a result of having abundant natural resources, countries' economic, political, and socioeconomic conditions deteriorate (Siegle 2008). Renewable, nonrenewable, depletable, and nondepletable resources such as hydrocarbons, natural gas, coal, minerals, and oil are also discussed in this study (all are natural resources focus of this study). The Dutch Disease was an economic phenomenon that occurred in the Netherlands during the 1960s. The

discovery of natural gas in the Netherlands harmed other industries' competitiveness. The real exchange rate increased as resource revenues increased. They are unable to learn about such assets or improve their balance of payments due to the exchange rate's consistency with oil and gas revenue (Korhonen and Juurikkala 2007). The case of the Netherlands is not exceptional, as many countries with lower endowments perform far worse (Auty 2001). However, some countries have